

An Alternative Solution to Achieve Women Empowerment through Kanyashree Prakalpa in West Bengal

Antarjita Deb¹

Abstract

Women empowerment promotes womens' sense of self-worth, their ability to determine their own choices and their right to influence social change for themselves and others. The five pillars of women empowerment are education, health, security, finance and emotion. The present study attempts to find out the plausible path to achieve the goal of women empowerment through utilizing Kanyashree one-time grant. Four representative blocks such as Bhangar-I, Budgebudge-II, Canning-II and Gosaba of South 24 Parganas district of West Bengal have been selected for this study. The perception of girl students of age group of not less than 18 years, on women empowerment, has been studied in respect of selected contributory variables. The outcomes of these correlations are not identical in all four blocks of the district. The present study also attempts to find out the administrative lacunae and prescribes the plausible solution through establishing harmonious relations among different field-level administrative agencies such as three-tier panchayat administration, school/college administration, rural public library administration, voluntary organisations, parental associations, Kanyashree clubs etc. for smooth implementation and monitoring of the Kanyashree Prakalpa. The study also found a dichromatic scenario existing in a block where on one side girls are getting skilled due to the efforts undertaken by block level administration and on the other hand, many other girls are getting married before 18 years of age, without completing their school education.

Introduction

Women empowerment has five components: women's sense of self-worth; their right to have and to determine choices; their right to have access to opportunities and resources; their right to have power to control their own lives, both within and outside the home; and their ability to influence the direction of social change to create a more just social and economic order, nationally and internationally. (UN Commission on the Status of Women, 2002)

In this context, education, training, awareness raising, building self-confidence, expansion of choices, increased access to and control over resources, and actions to transform the structures and institutions that reinforce and perpetuate gender discrimination and inequality are important tools for empowering women and girls to claim their rights. (European Institute for Gender Equality, 2024)

¹ UGC NET-JRF Scholar working in Public Administration
Email ID- antarjitadeb635@gmail.com

Empowering the so-called ‘weaker sex’ is the most challenging and crucial step towards removing obstacles from the lives of women. A woman is said to be truly empowered when she can take decisions for herself free from external pressure, thus indicating complete control of woman’s life in her own hands. It ensures the exercise of freedom of life and personal liberty. Empowerment women in socio-cultural sphere consists of ensuring their self-respect and dignity in society, increasing their ability to be a decision-maker, right to avail education, right to choose a religion or even a religion-free life and finally raise voice against unsocial activities.

In developed countries, women are at par with men in economic participation as reflected in their high Gross Domestic Product (GDP) rates. According to a report published by Barclays titled, “India's breakout moment”, India can achieve a GDP growth rate of 8% by ensuring that women account for more than half of the new workforce set to be created by 2030. But cases of dowry system, gender bias, sexual harassment etc. are some of the malices persisting in the Indian society till today. Now when the world is gearing up to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), India- both at the central and state government levels, should vigorously pursue the goals of SDG 5 (Gender Equality) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) which are most intimately associated the view of achieving women empowerment. (UN, 2015)

Educating girl children, resisting child marriage and female school dropout rates, creating safe conditions at workplaces, creation of more actively functioning Self-Help Groups and microfinance institutions, skilling them so as to make them eligible for job market etc. are some of the prominent strategies undertaken in India for achieving women empowerment.

Keywords: Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), Women Empowerment, Kanyashree Prakalpa etc.

Review of Literatures

A large number of studies have been conducted on the themes of women empowerment, relation between gender equality and sustainable development as well as on efficacy of women specific government interventions. A study by Sonowal and Moran (2019) shows that since women constitute half of the population therefore, it is important to emphasize the needs and interest of the women for the development of the society and nation at large. Empowering women through education is very essential to aware them about their rights and strengthen them to fight against the prevailing prejudices. Thus, gender equality is crucial to sustainable development and women are the central actors in pathways to sustainability and green transformation. Das et al (2005) are of the view that conditional cash transfers can increase welfare in the society, either by protecting people from their own irrationalities or by providing incentives for them to gather more information (if forced to send a child to school, parents will find out more about the value of education). Another study by Esha et al (2014) reveals that Bangladesh’s impressive gains in women’s health and education has been due to the sustained investments in schooling, which is

also crucial for ensuring food and nutritional security, thereby reducing gender gap in human capital. Nerine (2014) shows that education should not be versioned as a process aimed at turning disempowered women into empowered ones, but as a tool to better equip them with the confidence and skills to negotiate this path. Bhattacharya et al. (2022) shows in his study conducted in the Nadia district that in most cases, Kanyashree grants were being diverted for use in marriage and other non-educational purposes, thereby deviating from the goals of achieving women empowerment through longer period of educational attainment and financial empowerment through skilling.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study have been conceived as follows:

- i) To assess the socio-economic status of women in four CD blocks of South 24 Parganas district with selected indicators.
- ii) To examine the level of perception among Kanyashree beneficiaries regarding different dimensions of women empowerment, viz., social, economic etc.
- iii) To find out the role of administrators in being a part of empowering adolescent girls through implementation of the Kanyashree Prakalpa.
- iv) To study the existing administrative set-up in empowering women and suggests the plausible administrative reforms.

Methodology of the Study

The present study is based on the available secondary analysis of field level data as collected from four Community Development Blocks of West Bengal- which are Bhangar-I, Budgebudge-II, Canning-II and Gosaba. Qualitative analysis of the correlation between perception of girl students on women empowerment and some other important contributory variables has been done for the present study.

Analysis of Data

We are choosing South 24 Parganas district since it has the maximum difference between number of Kanyashree applications targeted by the district administration and number of actually sanctioned applications. Four Community Development Blocks, namely, Bhangar-I, Budgebudge-II, Canning-II and Gosaba have been purposefully chosen as the representative blocks of the whole South 24 Parganas district, covering East, West, North and South regions of the district.

Table : Correlation Analysis between perception of girl students on women empowerment and other selected contributory variables

Contributory Variables	‘r’ value for Bhangar-I	‘r’ value for Budgebudge-II	‘r’ value for Canning-II	‘r’ value for Gosaba
Learning position	Non-significant	Highly significant	Non-significant	Highly significant
How old the respondent is	Non-significant	Highly significant	Non-significant	Highly significant
Profession of guardians	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant
Parents’ monthly earning	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant
Earning of family per month	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant
Student’s attendance in School or College	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant
Food supply during school/college	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant
Power- supply at home	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant
Availability of Aadhar card	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Non-significant
Distance between institution and home	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant
Communication	Highly	Highly	Highly	Highly

to institution	significant	significant	significant	significant
Convenience of private tuition	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant
Efficacy of Kanyashree grant for dropout girls	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Non-significant
Family consent for study	Highly significant	Highly significant	Non-significant	Highly significant
Role of institutions for obtaining Kanyashree grant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Non-significant
Role of GP for obtaining Kanyashree Grant	Non-significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Non-significant
Responsibility of BDO for obtaining Kanyashree Grant	Non-significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Non-significant
Usefulness of Kanyashree grant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant
Influence on women empowerment	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant
Role of public services on women empowerment	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant
Encouragement regarding job-related work	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant
Contribution of	Non-significant	Highly	Non-significant	Highly

public libraries for providing information regarding women empowerment		significant		significant
--	--	-------------	--	-------------

While studying the correlation between perception of students on women empowerment and other selected contributory variables, it has been found that due to the high female education rate of Budgebudge-II and Gosaba blocks, girl students had got the learning support from their parents, whereas the opposite scenario is found in Bhangar-I and Canning-II blocks. The average age of respondents of Budgebudge-II and Gosaba blocks is comparatively higher than the other two blocks. As a result, respondents' perception on women empowerment is clearer than their counterparts in Bhangar-I and Canning-II blocks. South 24 Parganas is the only district in West Bengal where the maximum number of applications for Kanyashree scheme was rejected due to non-availability of Aadhar card of the beneficiaries. Out of these four blocks, this scenario was the most prominent in Gosaba block. In Gosaba block, it has been found that one of the purposes of continuing girls' education till 18 years was to get the Kanyashree one-time grant and as soon as the grant was received, the girls dropped out. This scenario is not the only scenario of Gosaba block but it is found in almost all blocks of West Bengal. Out of the four blocks, Canning-II is the exception in the sense that the higher education rate among girls is more than in other blocks. Due to negligence from part of school authorities, a good number of girl students could not apply for the Kanyashree Prakalpa in the correct way. The scenario is acute in Bhangar-I, Budgebudge-II and Canning-II blocks. This is one of the main reasons that the South 24 Parganas has maximum difference between number of Kanyashree applications targeted by the district administration and number of actually sanctioned applications. One of the prime hindrances in the way of successful implementation of Kanyashree Prakalpa is that the three-tier Panchayat administration, especially in the given district, was found to be lackadaisical in its approach towards active implementation and monitoring of the scheme. As a result, sensitization of parents and their wards was largely neglected due to the inactiveness of the Panchayat administration. The situation is worse in Budgebudge-II and Canning-II as compared to the other two blocks. Generally, Panchayat members are involved in pursuing the day-to-day affairs regarding the locality's development and other issues with the block level administration. Since

the Panchayat administration of Budgebudge-II and Canning-II are comparatively less active, hence the block level administration is also less active for these two blocks. For various reasons such as insufficient library staff, poor infrastructure, non-availability of funds, irregular functioning and non-availability of internet facilities, rural libraries, in most of the blocks, have failed to emerge as the prime agent for disseminating information about various government initiatives to actualize women empowerment amongst adolescent girls and other local people. The result of non-involvement of rural public libraries has been seen in Bhangar-I and Canning-II blocks in their negligible contribution in disseminating knowledge and information to the beneficiaries.

Conclusion

The block level administration of Budgebudge II was instrumental in arranging the skill development training courses such as tailoring, healthcare, beauty therapist, general duty assistant, web developer, domestic data entry operator etc. Apart from these, block level administration of Budgebudge-II has also arranged coaching for West Bengal Civil Service Examination exclusively for the Kanyashree girls. During 2019-20, twenty of such Kanyashree girls availed the coaching of West Bengal Civil Service Examination. (Akhter et al, 2020) On the other hand, it has also been observed that a good number of girl students who got married below 18 years of age in the same Budgebudge-II block. Such a mixed outcome has been found in the whole district of South 24 Parganas. The issue of women empowerment would still remain to be a far cry unless proper coordination mechanism amongst the various field level units responsible for implementation and monitoring of the scheme like the three-tier panchayat administration, school/college administration, rural public library administration, voluntary organisations, parental associations, Kanyashree clubs as well as the block development offices is ensured. Internet enabled rural libraries with adequate manpower and financial resources can become an important tool in ensuring an effective Knowledge, Education and Communication Strategy so as to successfully implement social development schemes like Kanyashree Prakalpa.

References

- Akhter, Y. et al. (2020). Students' Role in Women Empowerment through Public Libraries and Impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa of South 24 Parganas District of West Bengal, India. Shodh Sanchar Bulletin. Vol. 10, Issue 40.
- Bhattacharya et al. (2022). Assessment of Women Empowerment through Kanyashree Prakalpa: An Empirical Study in Nadia District of West Bengal, Unpublished Thesis.
- Das, J, Q-T Do, and B Özler. (2005). Reassessing Conditional Cash Transfer Programs, World Bank Research Observer. Vol. 20, No. 1. pp. 57–80.
- Esha et al. (2014). Women's Empowerment in agriculture: What Role for Food Security in Bangladesh?
- European Institute for Gender Equality. (2024). Retrieved from https://eige.europa.eu/publicationsresources/thesaurus/terms/1246?language_content_entity=en
- Nerine, G. (2014). Empowering women through education: Experiences from Dalit women in Nepal
- Sonowal. K. and Moran, K. (2019). Gender Equality for Sustainable Development in India- An Analytical Study. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention. Volume 8 Issue 02 Series. I
- United Nations. (UN, 2015). Retrieved on February 27, 2024 from <https://www.un.org/fast-facts/sustainable-development>
- UN Commission on the Status of Women. (2002). Agreed Conclusions on eradicating poverty, including through the empowerment of women throughout their life cycle, in a globalising world.